

Abandoned Lands in Mountainous Regions: Social and Ecological Values

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Rural abandonment in Eiritania - Greece (phoro by A. Pantera)

Abandoned land in mountain areas poses a complex set of challenges, opportunities and risks, particularly from a social and ecological perspective. When agricultural or livestock farming activities are halted, due to economic and social pressures, environmental degradation or, most notably, the migration of rural residents to urban centres, the land is abandoned and gradually forested. This has both positive and negative impacts on the surrounding community, the ecosystem and the wider area. Positive impacts include increased forest cover, reduced soil erosion and improved hydrological conditions. The negative impacts include loss of production, biodiversity, accessibility difficulties and increased risk of forest fires.

A representative example is the mountainous Eiritania as the former agricultural land in small lowland areas or terraces, which were used for the cultivation of cereals in the arid parts of the land and legumes and vegetables in the moist ones, which ensured the nutritional adequacy of the mountain households, have been abandoned for more than 50 years. Also many forest areas in the region are not grazed or are grazed to a much lesser extent now. In these areas, various forest species have established themselves, either in their entire area or in some places, which over time have created a pre-forest - forest vegetation structure. Changing the form of these lands does not mean that they have lost their value. Some of the abandoned farmland has been used in the last decades only for grazing small flocks of sheep and goats by the few herders who remain in the mountain communities. Grazing on these areas is very important for maintaining soil quality and managing native vegetation. In addition, these abandoned areas still retain in many cases the remains of old structures (terraces, wooden structures, water management networks and other water management works) and remnants of past agroforestry practices (cultivation techniques and old cultivars), which can be promoted and utilised within the framework of sustainable development to support local communities through sustainable land use practices such as agroforestry, agro-tourism, ecotourism and the conservation of natural resources.

For environmental and social reasons, it is necessary to reintegrate these abandoned agricultural areas back into agriculture by using them for traditional and new crops. Continuing to consider these areas as agricultural land is essential in the context of their future reversion to their past land use and the preservation of their value as assets of the local population, keeping the "gate" open for the return or resettlement of the mountain areas and their development.

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